

**SOCIOLOGICAL MEASUREMENT OF STUDENTS'
ENVIRONMENTAL BEHAVIOR**

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Abstract: The article reveals the theoretical and methodological foundations for the study of environmental behavior and identifies its features among students. Existing theoretical concepts that reveal ecological behavior are analyzed and the most relevant of them for studying the ecological behavior of students of TSTU in Almalyk are identified. The characteristic features of ecological behavior are revealed through the analysis of the ecological aspect of the lifestyle of student youth, carried out on the basis of their own empirical research. The types of ecological behavior of student youth are singled out according to the criterion of their involvement in ecological practices.

Keywords: social group, sociological research, ecological consciousness, ecological practice, ecological priorities.

Introduction

Global environmental problems have been formed over many generations as a result of consumer attitudes towards the natural environment. This problem is one of the most urgent in Uzbekistan, where, against the backdrop of high temperatures as a result of climate change, repeated atmospheric droughts, garimsels, dust storms are noted, as well as an increase in the amount of dust in residential areas of the population due to industrial enterprises, vehicles and landfills of the construction industry. .

Overcoming the ecological crisis caused by human activity is impossible without changes in the worldview of people, in their attitude to the world around them, without

raising the mass level of environmental consciousness and implementing environmental behavior into everyday practice.

Students as a large social group are one of the most active and receptive to changing conditions of life. It is the younger generation that is more willing to implement new behaviors, since it is more difficult for the older generation to abandon deeply learned habits [5].

The environmental behavior of student youth, on the one hand, depends on their active citizenship, personal interest, the level of environmental knowledge, responsible attitude to nature and the consolidation of environmental values in the general system of values of youth. On the other hand, the formation of environmental behavior is influenced by external factors - the social institutions of society: the state, the education system (from kindergarten to university), the media, the activities of environmental organizations. The institute of higher education is the key institution in the process of shaping the ecological behavior of student youth.

The relevance of the chosen topic of this study is determined by: 1) insufficient theoretical and methodological development in the sociological literature of Uzbekistan of the problems of environmental behavior; 2) the lack of empirical data to adequately assess the current level of development of students' environmental behavior, the role of one or another factor influencing environmental behavior; 3) the need to educate an environmentally responsible personality, the formation of certain "environmentally friendly" types of student behavior as a social subject, corresponding to the principles and goals of the development of society in the "nature-society-man" system.

Methodology

Environmental problems in foreign social science have long attracted the attention of scientists, including in recent decades, when a sharp aggravation of the environmental situation in the world forced us to reconsider the set of priorities and values at the global level and highlight environmental priorities (W. Beck [2], K. Welzel, E. Giddens, R. Dunlap, R [3], Inglehart, W. Catton, P. Stern).

In the proposed study, the socio-ecological concept of the representatives of the Chicago School of Sociology (R. Park, L. Wirth, R. Mackenzie, A. Hawley) was analyzed; the concept of sustainable development; the concept of a "new ecological paradigm" (W. Catton, R. Dunlap); the concept of post-material values (R. Inglehart, K. Welzel); the concept of risk society (W. Beck, E. Giddens, O.N. Yanitsky [10]); the concept of cultural trauma (J. Alexander [1], N. Smelser, P. Sztompka).

The focus of the Chicago School of Sociology was the influence of natural, environmental factors on a person and his life. Thanks to the development of this concept, new methods of empirical research have emerged, such as participant observation, the biographical method, territorial zoning, and social mapping [9].

The concept of sustainable development is a synthesis of three main components: economic, social and environmental. The task of sustainable development is the balance of economic, social and environmental components and their translation into the framework of specific activities. From the point of view of the environmental component, this concept is largely aimed at reducing environmental risks as factors hindering sustainable development. The concept of "new ecological paradigm" by W. Catton and R. Dunlap [3] states a different approach to the problem of interaction between man and nature, which was formulated in the following provisions: 1) in contrast to the principle of human exclusivity, which underlies the old ecological paradigms, man is one of the many living beings that are included in the global biophysical environment; 2) human dependence on the natural environment, which is complex and not always predictable; 3) culture and technological progress are limited by environmental laws.

The developers of the concept of post-material values R. Inglehart and K. Welzel [5] believe that the carriers of post-materialistic values are more susceptible to environmental risks, since they are better protected from the economic side than the carriers of material values.

Based on the theoretical and methodological analysis of the literature, it was concluded that the most promising is the consideration of environmental behavior within the framework of the concepts of risk society and cultural trauma. This is due

to the fact that risks are an integral characteristic of modern society, society cannot overcome them, but can minimize them through the formation of appropriate behavior, which will be aimed at protecting and protecting the environment. When considering ecological behavior, we use the definition given by I.A. Sosunova. According to this approach, environmental behavior is understood as an external manifestation of activity, which is characterized by specific positions and attitudes, the transformation of activity into real actions in relation to significant environmental problems, subjects and objects that affect the environment [7]. Based on the indicators available in the literature for measuring the practical implementation of such behavior in our study, certain criteria were selected, which will be discussed below.

In the practice of a specific sociological study, the most productive is the interpretation of ecological consciousness through an emphasis on the components that make up its structure. In this case, by ecological consciousness we mean a certain level of people's concern about the state of the environment, the level of ecological knowledge, the presence of a set of post-material values and attitudes in the subject, the recognition of a healthy and safe living environment as an important social value, and the awareness of the need for personal participation in environmental practices.

The choice of the object of study in this case is not accidental, since the problem of ecology mainly concerns future development, therefore environmental risks become especially acute for the younger generation.

Results and discussion

The study was conducted among students of the Almalyk branch of TSTU.

It should be noted that the concentration of mining enterprises in the city of Almalyk and its environs is very high, which makes it one of the industrial giants of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The Almalyk Mining and Metallurgical Combine (AGMK) is located and operates here with its numerous plants and processing plants, tailings (with an area of 1783 hectares and 800 million tons of waste), the Kalmakyr, Yoshlik I and Yoshlik II quarries with their dumps , as well as other ore mines of underground mining, the chemical plant of JSC "Ammophos". The ecological situation in the area is quite tense, which is associated with the consequences of emissions of

harmful substances, industrial enterprises and quarries of JSC AGMK into the atmosphere, water environment, and soil. So, around the tailing dump of JSC AGMK and industrial wastes of JSC Ammophos, the level of soil pollution with copper exceeds the background content by up to 10.3 and 8.2 times, respectively. In addition to copper, other toxic elements such as Pb, Zn, As, Sb, W, V are observed in soils around the tailing dump to a depth of 10 m, exceeding the MPC by 5–8 times [8].

The environmental impact of enterprises on the environment is very significant, the negative consequences of which have been noted for many decades in the atmosphere, water environment, soil, vegetation and changes in the natural landscape of the area. “The extraction of mineral resources is accompanied by drilling and blasting mining, releasing a lot of dust, carbon dioxide and hydrocarbons into the atmosphere, the content of which in the air affects the climatic conditions of the area (humidity, temperature, transparency, etc.” [9].

Peculiarities of ecological behavior and ecological consciousness of student youth studying in Almalyk were identified based on the analysis of the following measurements: the relevance of environmental problems in students' assessments; level of ecological knowledge; environmental values and attitudes of student youth; environmental behavior and types of environmental behavior of students.

The overall level of concern about environmental problems on a five-point scale was 3.4 points. The most urgent environmental problems for the city of Almalyk, according to students, are the following: industrial pollution, urban transport emissions and air pollution.

Based on the results of a sociological study, the characteristic features of the environmental behavior of student youth are highlighted: a) low level of involvement in group environmental practices; b) insufficiently active ecological position, manifested through individual ecological practices; c) anthropocentric orientation of the lifestyle associated with insufficient level of environmental knowledge, the secondary nature of environmental values in the general system of values of students and a low degree of awareness of one's own responsibility in matters of protecting and

protecting the environment. These features predetermine the low level of involvement of student youth in environmental practices.

A contradiction was revealed: on the one hand, students express a desire and willingness to change their lifestyle towards an environmentally oriented one, and on the other hand, this desire is not reflected in the actual environmental practices of students. Judging by the responses, the vast majority of students (79%) do not take specific actions aimed at improving the environment. This may indicate a weak or rather low degree of involvement of student youth in environmental practices.

On the basis of cluster analysis, three types of environmental behavior of students were identified depending on their involvement in certain environmental practices: included type (19%), non-included type (56%), excluded type (25%).

The included type is distinguished by a high level of involvement in environmental practices, initiative and active participation in specific environmental events, as well as a high level of environmental awareness. The non-included type is characterized by a lower level of involvement in environmental practices compared to the included type, with a desire and willingness to participate in environmental activities, as well as a sufficient level of environmental knowledge. The excluded type is distinguished by the practical absence of involvement in environmental practices, a low degree of environmental concern, and a low level of environmental awareness.

Among the types we have identified, only the included type is closest to the type of behavior that corresponds to modern challenges to society and the environmental situation: this type is distinguished by the highest level of knowledge revealed, a fairly high level of activity and initiative, and a high assessment of environmental values.

Insufficient level of environmental knowledge and low level of student youth awareness are confirmed by students' answers to questions about their knowledge of existing environmental organizations and city programs aimed at protecting and protecting the environment. Most students do not have a clear understanding of the goals and objectives of these programs and organizations, or do not know about them at all. The importance of improving information support is indicated by students' answers to the question of what actions they would recommend to take to improve the

environment. Along with financial incentives for enterprises and individuals that are involved in the protection and protection of the environment, tightening of legislation in the field of environmental safety, students pointed to the need to inform the population about the environmental problems of the city, public campaigns / actions aimed at raising concern about the environmental problems of the city and the need to improve the quality of environmental education in schools and universities of the city.

In the minds of the younger generation, anthropocentric attitudes retain priority over environmental attitudes. The rating of students' life priorities shows that environmental values turned out to be less significant than the values of health, family values, work and material well-being. The most significant of all the environmental values presented are such values as favorable environmental conditions and the conservation of natural resources. Attention is drawn to the fact that participation in environmental campaigns occupies the last places in the rating of environmental values, and in general in the system of student youth values.

Conclusion

A study of the ecological consciousness of Almalyk students showed that the respondents' high assessment of their behavior as environmentally oriented does not correspond to their level of environmental activity, which, according to the survey results, can be characterized as low. Young people, although they are concerned about the problem of the environment, do not believe in an environmental apocalypse in the foreseeable future. The hope for an improvement in the ecological situation is associated not with a change in the thinking and behavior of individuals, but with technological progress. Boys and girls do not intend to change their way of life also because they do not observe unecological behavior, transferring all responsibility for environmental pollution to others, assigning a decisive role in solving the environmental problem to various authorities. As a result, environmental issues have not yet entered the everyday life of young people, which is reflected in their social practices.

The rating of life priorities of student youth shows that environmental values turned out to be less significant than the values of health, family values, work and

material well-being. Students place the responsibility for solving environmental problems, first of all, on the state. At the same time, there is a growing sense of responsibility among the students themselves and the realization that changes must begin with ordinary citizens, which we noted as a positive moment.

The formation of environmental behavior of students is influenced by both internal factors (the level of environmental knowledge of citizens, the priority of environmental values in consciousness and behavior, a sense of responsibility towards and in interaction with nature), and external factors (institutions such as family, education, state, mass media, activities of environmental organizations). It is also important to take into account the fact that "the national model of civil society in Uzbekistan is due to its historical and socio-cultural characteristics, as well as national culture and traditional values, which, of course, had an impact on the formation of the environmental movement in the country." [6, p. 152].

The results of the conducted sociological research show that environmental education within higher education is not yet focused on the formation of students' environmental behavior: it is not given the importance that it should occupy as a factor in ensuring the sustainable development of society. The level of information about their activities and ongoing activities on the part of environmental organizations is also insufficient. Therefore, first of all, it is advisable to activate the environmental orientation of education so that the inclusion of young people in environmental practices is motivated by relevant values.

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